

**METHODS OF PREPARATION OF PHYTOPREPARATIONS FROM
MEDICINAL PLANTS CONTAINING PURIFIC SUBSTANCES AND
COUMARINS PRESERVATIVES AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THEIR
USE**

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Abstract. Nowadays, as a result of our increasing need for medicine, most of the patients are suffering from side effects after making various prescriptions for themselves. Due to such problems, in this article, we have set ourselves the goal of preparing guidelines for the preparation of phytopreparations from medicinal plants containing food additives and coumarins.

Key words: Additive, coumarin, dicoumarin, phytocontrol, prescription, spell, capsule, skin disease.

INTRODUCTION.

The number of enterprises in the system increased sharply as a result of the special attention paid to the pharmaceutical sector in the following years at the initiative of the President. Several regulations have been adopted over the years. As a result of this, it can be noted that during the pandemic, it was possible to provide our people with high-quality and cheap medicines, and the medicines produced in our country were exported to about 20 countries in order to meet the domestic needs. But the scope of our tasks is wide.

The population of our country is increasing, and the demand for cheap and modern medicines is increasing year by year. The creation of new privileges and opportunities in the field is an important factor in the quality production of medicines. The decree of the head of our state "On additional measures for the rapid

development of the pharmaceutical industry of the republic in 2022-2026" is of great importance as it is aimed at the rapid development of the industry.

MAIN PART

Lactones obtained from plants that are products of coumarin (cis-ortho-oxidolchin) acid are called coumarins. Cis-ortho-oxydolcinic acid and its products are not found in almost pure form in nature. These acids release a molecule of water and quickly turn into the corresponding lactones. Therefore, coumarins are also considered as benzo-a-pyrone products. Coumarin itself is a lactone of cis-ortho-oxidolcinic acid.

Cis-o-hydroxycinnamic
(o-coumaric) acid

Koumarin
(9,10-benzo- α -pyrone)

The initial compound of coumarins - coumarin was first identified in 1820 by Fogel from *Dipteryx odorata* Willd. (*Coumarouna odorata*, belongs to the leguminous family) is isolated from the fruit of the plant. The chemical structure of coumarins was determined by Perkin in 1877. In addition, the Fragrant *ruta-Ruta graveolens* L. plant is one of the plants rich in coumarin. Modern medical applications of coumarin derivatives are used as anticoagulant drugs to treat blood clots and prevent deep vein thrombosis.

Coumarin was first used to prevent and treat blood clots in the 1920s and was considered a therapeutic drug.

If we pay attention to the way of life of the animal world living in the wild nature, they knew how to eat medicinal plants rich in various biologically active substances to protect their health. For example, animals living in areas with cold temperatures and high rainfall have learned that by eating plants rich in nutrients, it is useful to increase the tension of skin pigments.

Additives combine with protein substances of the skin and form an insoluble compound. As a result, the skin of animals becomes waterproof, rot-resistant, elastic and similar properties. Non-poisonous complex organic compounds of high molecular weight, consisting of polyatomic phenols and obtained from medicinal plants, are called tannins.

Tanids are widespread in nature, especially in dicotyledonous families, such as Rosaceae, Fabaceae, Saxifragaceae, Polygonaceae, Salicaceae, Fagaceae, Anacardiaceae, and it is common in other families.

Acidic substances take an active part in the oxidation and reduction reactions that occur constantly in plant tissues, first of all, in the process of cellular respiration. Since the preservatives have bactericidal and fungicidal effects, they protect the wood part of trees from rapid rotting.

Medicinal preparations made from spices and products containing tannins are used in medicine for the treatment of diseases of the gastrointestinal tract (diarrhea, colitis), inflammation of the mucous membranes of the mouth and throat (stomatitis, gingivitis), skin burns, chronic eczema, and wounds. used as an astringent and bactericidal agent and to stop bleeding from the intestines.

Tannin has astringent, antiseptic and anti-inflammatory effects. It treats gastrointestinal diseases (gastro-intestinal catarrh, enteritis, colitis, diarrhea), inflammation of the oral cavity, nose and throat, as well as burns, chronic eczema and various wounds (moist wound, purulent wound) is used in treatment.

CONCLUSION

From the above information, it can be concluded that flavoring substances are found in families belonging to the class of dicotyledonous plants, for example, Rosaceae, Fabaceae, Saxifragaceae, Polygonaceae, Salicaceae, Fagaceae, Pistachio.

It has been found to be abundant in Anacardiaceae and other families. Medicinal phytopreparations prepared from products containing tannins are used in medicine for the treatment of gastrointestinal (diarrhea, colitis), inflammation of the mucous membranes of the mouth and throat (stomatitis, gingivitis), skin burns, chronic eczema and wounds. is used. We concluded that medicinal preparations rich in

coumarins are useful in modern medicine as anticoagulant drugs for the treatment of blood clots and prevention of deep vein thrombosis.

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